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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THEORETICAL, METHODOLOGICAL, AND PRACTICAL FACTORS OF DIFFERENTIATED EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article examines the purpose, types, factors, stages, methods, concepts, and advantages of differentiated instruction as a pedagogical and psychological problem, as well as the pedagogical and psychological conditions associated with its implementation. It also reflects the views and comparative analyses of Eastern and Western thinkers and contemporary scholars on this topic.

Key words: differentiated instruction, type, factor, stage, method, concept, stratified group, individual abilities, intellectual level, monitoring, teaching principle.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tabaqalashtirilgan ta'limning pedagogik-psixologik muammo sifatidagi maqsadi, turlari, omillari, bosqichlari, usullari, tushunchalari va afzalliklari, shuningdek, uni amalga oshirish bilan bog'liq pedagogik-psixologik shart-sharoitlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, Sharq va G'arb mutafakkirlari hamda zamonaviy olimlarning bu boradagi qarashlari va ularning qiyosiy tahlili o'z aksini topgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tabaqalashtirilgan ta'lim, tur, omil, bosqich, usul, tushuncha, tabaqalashtirilgan guruh, individual qobiliyatlar, intellektual daraja, monitoring, o'qitish prinsipi.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются цель, виды, факторы, этапы, методы, концепции и преимущества дифференцированного обучения как педагогической и психологической проблемы, а также педагогические и психологические условия, связанные с его организацией. Отражены также взгляды и сравнительный анализ восточных и западных мыслителей и современных учёных по данной проблеме.

Ключевые слова: дифференцированное обучение, вид, фактор, этап, метод, концепция, стратифицированная группа, индивидуальные способности, интеллектуальный уровень, мониторинг, принцип обучения.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern education system, organizing lessons based on the individual characteristics and the level of knowledge of students is considered one of the pressing issues. Especially at the primary education stage, since pupils' cognitive activity, speech abilities, and levels of thinking differ, differentiated education is considered an important factor for effective teaching.

In higher educational institutions, mastering the methodology of differentiated teaching of the mother tongue subject by future primary school teachers ensures an increase in lesson quality and helps pupils thoroughly master the fundamentals of various subjects. Mother tongue lessons play a leading role in developing pupils' and students' thinking, communication, and creative skills. Therefore, differentiated teaching of the mother tongue increases each pupil's opportunities for individual development based on quality education.

On this matter, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, in his speeches particularly emphasized: "... the quality of education depends on the quality of the teacher's methodological training. Every teacher must master modern methods and be able to approach our children individually" [7]. This article discusses the pedagogical and psychological problems of differential education.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

In pedagogical and encyclopedic explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language, the word competence is explained as "a person's awareness of a particular field, the level of knowledge in that field," while the word differential (from Latin *differentia* – difference, distinction) means "an approach adapted to students' individual needs, abilities, and learning styles during the educational process" [8 – 630; 9 – 85; 10 – 319]. Thus, differential education

is a teaching principle, method, and tool aimed at increasing effectiveness by adapting the teaching process to students' and pupils' personal individual abilities, intellectual levels, learning pace, and needs.

In the East and West, differential education has long been viewed with great interest. In particular, in Islamic teaching, the thinker Al-Haliliy emphasized the individual needs of students of knowledge, advancing the idea of considering differences in their spiritual, moral, and intellectual development during the educational process [14]. Confucius, Plato, Quintilian, and Aristotle emphasized that differentiated education should be adapted to the needs of different classes in society, stressing that the goal of education should not be limited only to imparting knowledge but should also serve the moral and social development of the individual.

In ancient Babylon, studies on individual differences in humans gave particular importance to Francis Galton's activity in analyzing abilities. Galton scientifically substantiated the necessity of paying attention in teaching to aspects such as an individual's responses to various stimuli, reaction speed, perception of color, and evaluation of differences in the weight of objects. Although the views of ancient scholars on organizing education according to the needs of society's classes differ from today's ideas about differential education, it should be acknowledged that their attitude and evaluations toward differentiated education stemmed from the demands of their era and society.

Confucius considered education important for different strata of society, emphasizing that people must learn moral and social responsibility appropriate to their status, thus raising the issue of differentiated education. Quintilian considered education necessary for all classes, and in his view, education should be the main means for the development of all members of society. In his work *On the Art of Oratory*, the scholar explained the importance of education for society and its classes. Although the views of ancient scholars on organizing education according to the needs of social strata differ from today's ideas about differentiated education, their perspectives can be regarded as laying the foundation for differentiated learning.

The classical (traditional) founders of the ideas of differential education are recognized as Y. G. Pestalozzi, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, L. Vygotsky, John Dewey, K. D. Ushinsky, A. Avloni, and other famous pedagogues. Their views on differential education reflected ideas of student-centered teaching that took individual characteristics into account.

In the formation of modern differential education, foreign and local pedagogical experience and contemporary psychological research play an important role. These approaches are closely connected with educational ideas such as inclusive education, student-centered learning, and the competency-based approach.

John Dewey's idea that the educational process should be based on the student's personal experience is considered an important source for understanding the philosophical foundations of differential education [12].

According to Z. E. Chorshanbiyev, students' intellectual abilities are naturally diverse [13–36]. The scholar's idea expresses that in differential teaching, consideration of students' various abilities forms the basis for developing teaching methods adapted to them.

Academician R. H. Jo'rayev emphasizes that differential education creates the opportunity to develop students and pupils by providing each of them with information corresponding to their level of preparation [14–23].

T. A. Segeda and A. N. Petrova propose understanding differentiation as an educational system that provides every student, even those with a minimum level of preparation in subject fundamentals, the guaranteed opportunity and full right to adapt to constantly changing social conditions and to choose the field most suitable to their inclinations [15–33; 16–113].

The well-known foreign scholar Carol Ann Tomlinson describes differential education as a teaching strategy based on students' needs, stressing that this approach should be adapted to students' levels of knowledge, experience, learning styles, and motivations [17].

Professor H. Sh. Qodirov believes that differentiated education, considering students' learning speed and level, should be based on adapting educational materials to foster their convergence in individual and group activities. According to B. M. Utegenova, differentiated education means that students assimilate the same concepts or subject content at different levels, relying on their individual characteristics [2–76].

In psychology, the term "differentiation" was first used by German psychologist W. Stern. He was one of the first to develop the concept of the psychology of individual differences, based on gathering information about differences between people. The term "differential psychology" appeared only at the beginning of the 20th century, but the problem of differences between people had already attracted the attention of ancient thinkers and scholars. According to the well-known psychologist K. S. Muxsinova, differentiated education, by properly nurturing the gifted, transforms them into "ideally developed adults" and lays the foundation for great success in real life. Therefore, in preserving and developing students' talents, differentiated education carries significant social importance [4–69–76].

According to R. Slavin, the effectiveness of differential education requires identifying students' individual cognitive needs and demands, developing appropriate educational technologies for them, and organizing a learning experience adapted to students' individual needs, abilities, and learning styles [3–57].

Based on the opinions expressed by leading foreign and domestic scholars regarding this issue, and following their reasoning, we expressed our own authorial definition of differentiated education in the following form: differentiated education is the educational process organized by dividing students and pupils into various strata – groups, taking into account their individual abilities, interests, levels of preparation, and experiences. It is a method of general development based on providing (or receiving) information (knowledge) suitable to each student's level of preparation, experience, and ability.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology in this scientific article focused on the process of collecting and analyzing data. The required information was obtained from scientific literature, official documents, advanced pedagogical practices, and practical observations. The collected data were processed through comparison, content analysis, and generalization methods to ensure the scientific validity of the research results. Statistical data were also analyzed to identify interconnections and possibilities for practical application. Thus, the research methodology was structured on the basis of concrete evidence and theoretical approaches.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The article reveals the essence of the main pedagogical, psychological, social, methodological, and organizational factors influencing differentiated education. Z. Nazarova acknowledges that understanding differentiation factors and applying them correctly guarantees the increase of each student's cognitive opportunities ^[5], while D. Rahimova emphasizes that considering differentiation factors not only increases the effectiveness of education but also serves to create social stability and equal opportunities ^[6].

Furthermore, differentiated education varies depending on students' cognition, gender, interests, intellectual development level, personal-psychological types, and health condition. In ancient times, the basis of differentiated education was gender distinction, i.e., teaching boys and girls separately; however, in later years, this type of differentiation has lost much of its relevance. In this work, internal and external types of differentiation – within a class or group – are distinguished. Internal differentiation refers to teaching students in one group by dividing them into important subgroups based on different characteristics, while external differentiation refers to teaching in stable groups that differ in content, teaching methods, and organizational forms.

In this work, the components of differential education activity for future primary school teachers are identified as theoretical knowledge, practical experience, application of advanced methods and technologies, experience sharing, monitoring, and assessment, with the necessity of their scientific substantiation.

Today, in scientific-methodical sources, numerous concepts such as “differentiation,” “differential education,” “differential approach,” “individualization,” and “stratification” are used, and their meanings and essence are interpreted differently. In the following table, we presented definitions and explanations of these concepts provided by certain dictionaries and scholars.

Table 1: Interpretation of existing explanations of the concept of differentiated education

Sources	Expressed Explanations
Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan	Organizing education on a differential basis is founded on the following: – In differential education, the teacher organizes the content of education for a group of learners based on their important existing qualities; – It ensures the specialization of the educational process for various selected groups of learners; – Differentiation is a distinctive form of individualization of the educational process.
B. M. Bim-Bad. Pedagogical Encyclopedic Dictionary	A differential approach to teaching is an adaptive approach to each learner, based on their abilities and academic achievements.
M. K. Akimova. Psychophysiological Characteristics of School Students	Differentiated education envisions the creation of relatively stable or temporary learning groups that differ by certain features – content, level of learning requirements, interests, forms of teaching, and others.
G. V. Dorofeev et al.	Differentiation in teaching is education that provides each learner with the opportunity to adapt to constantly changing conditions and is directed, to a large extent, toward meeting their inclinations.
I. M. Osmolovskaya. The Process of Differentiated Education in the Modern School	Individualization is the final form of differentiation, in which the learning process is organized not by groups, but by taking into account the characteristics of each individual student. Differentiation, in turn, is the method of organizing the learning process based on the individual typological characteristics of the person – abilities, interests, inclinations, features of intellectual activity, and others.

R. Safarova. Some Issues of Transition to Differentiated Education

Differentiating the content of education based on students' interests, abilities, aspirations, and needs is an effective approach to organizing the learning process, creating favorable conditions for the student's personality to express itself.

In the sources, the main mechanisms of differentiated education – such as the use of individual and group learning, adapted and interactive teaching methods, project-based learning, problem-based teaching, didactic games, and collaborative learning – are identified and specifically described. In addition, this article examines the main concepts of the development of differential education, their founders, and, in particular, the unique features and specialized approaches of each concept. Its individual learning, group learning, competency-based approach, and constructivism concepts are distinguished and presented separately in tabular form.

Table 2: Main Concepts of Differentiated Teaching

Concepts	Founder	Essence
Individual learning	L. S. Vygotsky, A. N. Leontiev	Taking into account students' zones of proximal development and personal capabilities.
Group learning	K. D. Ushinsky, B. P. Yesipov	Dividing students into groups according to their abilities, interests, and level of knowledge.
Competency-based approach	J. Raven, M. A. Choshanov	Achieving and assessing educational outcomes through specific competencies.
Constructivism	J. Piaget	Students construct knowledge based on their existing experience.

The main goal of all these concepts in differentiated teaching of the mother tongue subject is to develop each student's language, speech, and thinking ability, to teach them independent analysis, and to guide them toward creativity. Below, the system of differential education in Uzbekistan is compared, based on key parameters, with the existing approaches in countries with developed education and economies such as Finland, Germany, Japan, and the USA, and is presented in tabular form.

Table 3: Comparative Table of Differential Education

Parameters	Uzbekistan	Developed Countries (Finland, Germany, Japan, USA)
Approach	Mainly standardized, the same approach for everyone	Approach based on individual abilities, interests, and needs
Grouping	Limited selection practice in schools or universities	Early-stage orientation according to ability and interest
Teaching methods	Mainly traditional, lecture-based	Interactive, experience-based, problem-based teaching
Curricula	A single curriculum for all	Personalized learning paths, modular system
Teacher training	Limited retraining process	Highly qualified, regular retraining
Inclusivity and equality	Insufficient infrastructure for people with disabilities	Equal opportunities for all, highly developed inclusive education
Community participation	Low level of parental involvement	Active opportunities to participate in the educational process and advisory bodies
Assessment of results	Mainly based on tests and written exams	Objective and multifaceted assessment; portfolio, project, reflection elements

It is evident that differential education – as a pedagogical-psychological issue – requires future primary school teachers to possess comprehensive knowledge about the factors, types, principles, concepts, tasks, and unique psychological characteristics, mechanisms, and comparative analysis of differential education competence.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, differential education, as a pedagogical-psychological issue, has been studied by many scholars, and there exist various positive opinions regarding its significance, methodological foundations, and practical importance. Differential education is considered an important factor in ensuring the development of the individual, the state, and society through the development of students' individual abilities, the enhancement of cognitive effectiveness, and the adaptation of the educational process.

Furthermore, differentiated education plays a crucial role in creating equal opportunities for learners with different intellectual levels, interests, and personal-psychological characteristics. By considering individual differences, it enables teachers to apply modern pedagogical technologies, thereby fostering creativity, independent thinking, and problem-solving skills among pupils.

Another important aspect is that differential education contributes to social stability by reducing inequality in education, ensuring inclusivity, and promoting lifelong learning. This, in turn, leads to the preparation of competitive specialists who are able to adapt to the demands of the rapidly changing global environment.

Based on the conducted analysis, it can be suggested that future teachers should be provided with systematic training in differentiated instruction, continuous professional development, and access to innovative teaching resources. It is also advisable to expand research in this field, taking into account both local experiences and international best practices, in order to strengthen the theoretical and methodological foundations of differential education.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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